

DEVELOPMENT OF DUCTILE-HYBRID COMPOSITES (DHC) BY THE BRAIDTRUSION PROCESS

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SUMMARY

Ductile-hybrid composites (DH-C) for civil engineering infrastructure have been developed at Villanova University and AMPEL, University of British Columbia. A variety of products, including internal concrete FRP reinforcement and structural shapes, mimic the behaviour of steel with bi-linear or tri-linear stress-strain behaviour (elastic, plastic, strain hardening).

Keywords: Braided Composites, Ductility, Hybrids, Infrastructure/ Civil Engineering

INTRODUCTION

Reinforced concrete (R/C) structures, especially pavements and bridge decks that constitute vital elements of the infrastructure of all industrialized societies, are deteriorating prematurely. Structural repair and upgrading of these structural elements have become a more economical option for constructed facilities especially in the United States and Canada. Fiber-Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) have been used to remedy this; however, current FRPs fail in a brittle manner. Ductile-hybrid fiber reinforced polymers (DH-FRP) for civil engineering infrastructure have been developed at Villanova University and AMPEL, University of British Columbia.

DH-FRP is produced using a combination of both traditional pultrusion and braiding processes simultaneously, creating a 'Braidtrusion' process [2, 3]. The structure of the DH-FRP materials can be comprised of either or both geometric and material hybrid systems [2]. The concept of DH-FRP was to design a material that had a stress-strain behavior similar to that of conventional steel members. This means that the material should have high initial stiffness, a definite yield point, and plastic and strain hardening stress-strain behavior. This is achievable by careful material selection and through innovative architectural design.

The material hybrid system used for DH-FRP utilizes materials with a mismatch of material properties including fiber stiffness and fiber ultimate strain. The geometric hybridization can be either 1) a braided structure (sleeve) with an elastic core or 2) an

over-braided structure with various braid orientations. Both geometric systems follow the hierarchical design methodology [1-3].

For the sleeve/core architecture, the sleeve consists of a braided structure and can be tailored to develop members of constant cross sections (e.g., DH-FRP structural shapes) or members with deformed cross-sections (e.g., DH-FRP rebars). The core yarns act as a mandrel for the braided sleeve. To obtain maximum member stiffness, the core yarns were oriented uni-directionally. This system relies on both material and geometric hybridization to obtain ductility. For the over-braided structure, consecutive over-braids at various fiber orientations were performed over a mandrel (e.g., balsa core). This allows for a controlled and progressive failure mechanism. This system can solely rely on geometric hybridization to obtain ductility.

Two fiber architecture models were developed including 1) a Fiber Architecture Analysis Model (FAAM) and 2) a Composite Architecture Design Model (CADM). The FAAM predicts the general stress-strain properties of existing composites comprised of either DH-FRP or unidirectional constructions while the CADM designs the material based on a desired stress-strain or load-displacement behavior.

Two experimental programs were conducted: 1) development of DH-FRP rebars for reinforced concrete members and 2) structural shapes including rectangular structural tubes with a balsa core. Results demonstrate a bi-linear or tri-linear stress-strain behaviour with sufficient stiffness and significant ductility. Preliminary results also indicate that reinforced concrete members reinforced with DH-FRP bars exhibit sufficient ductility for earthquake applications.

THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT

A computer Fiber Architecture Analysis Model (FAAM) was developed to obtain the general stress-strain properties of DH-FRP bars. The model was valid for any material system, geometry, and bar architecture. A Composite Architecture Design Model (CADM) was developed to verify experimental results. A spectrum of material hybrid systems with various fiber orientations and fiber volume fractions were studied. The model study included a variety of products, including various internal concrete FRP reinforcement and structural shapes including W-shapes, tubes, and angles. All members showed multi-linear stress-strain behaviour (elastic, plastic, strain hardening).

Background

The impetus of this model was to develop a generalized design module that would enable a material designer to design a braided hybrid element of any size, architecture, geometry, or material system. The element could either be a braided element with constant cross section, a non-uniform cross section with rib yarns incorporated, or an element with or without an elastic core, depending on the need of the designer. Also, various design concepts using multiple yarn systems could be developed. The experimental results of the DH-FRP elements were used to verify the validity of the design models.

The behavior of ductile composites can be predicted using a modified rule of mixtures. DH-FRPs are designed such that the core fails before the braided section of the structure. As such, the yielding behavior of the composite is created when the core fails and the stress is transferred to the surrounding braid. Therefore, the yield strain, ε_{yield} is the ultimate strain of the core fiber, $\varepsilon_{c_{ult}}$ given by Equation 1.

$$\varepsilon_{yield} = \varepsilon_{c_{ult}} \quad (1)$$

The yield stress is the sum of the stresses at yield strain in the core yarns, the braid yarns, and the matrix. The contribution of each part of the composite is a function of the fiber volume fractions of the braid, the core, and the matrix, given by Equation 2. Once the core yarns break, the lower bound of the yield behavior is a result of the stress in the braid yarns at yield strain and the matrix, Equation 3.

$$\sigma_{yield} = V_{f_b} \sigma_{yield_b} + V_{f_c} \sigma_{ult_c} + V_m \sigma_{yield_m} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{yield_{lower}} = V_{f_b} \sigma_{yield_b} + V_m \sigma_{yield_m} \quad (3)$$

The ultimate stress and strain of the composite structure are dictated by the braid angle, θ , as seen in Equations 4 and 5. Increasing the braid angle will increase the strain capacity of the composite but decrease the ultimate strength of the composite. In order to offset the effects of steeper braid angles, the fiber volume fraction of the braided section must be increased, Equation 5. Shown in Figure 1 is the design concept of DH-FRP bars for internal concrete reinforcement.

$$\varepsilon_{ult} = \frac{\varepsilon_{b_{ult}}}{\cos^2(\theta_b)} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{ult} = V_{f_b} \sigma_{ult_b} \cos^2(\theta_b) + V_m \sigma_{ult_m} \quad (5)$$

Figure 1: Design concept of braided DH-FRP bars.

An example of the bi-linear stress-strain behavior, resulting from the braiding effect is given in Figure 2. This is a representative stress-strain plot of a DH-FRP rebar manufactured by braiding Kevlar 49 around a carbon fiber core (Grafil34-12K WD).

Figure 2: Theoretical stress strain behavior of DH-FRP rebar.

This approach to analysis of the composite section assumes that all of the fibers in a specific layer or cross-section fail simultaneously, implying that all of the fibers in the cross-section are under uniform tension at the time of failure. However, it is extremely difficult and impractical to obtain uniform tension in all of the fibers throughout the structure's cross-section. As such, individual fibers and yarn bundles fail at different times throughout the test causing a progressive failure at yield, which has been verified experimentally.

The process used to design a given composite structure with a desired stress-strain behavior will result in the amount of yarn, or total denier of yarn required for a composite structure with a prescribed cross-sectional area. The design program (CADM) assumes a fiber volume fraction of the composite of 35 percent and calculates the strength and strain properties of the structure accordingly. If the strength of the composite is less than that required by the user, the fiber volume fraction is increased by 0.0001, and the process is repeated. The iteration continues until the required strength as per user input is reached. The maximum allowable fiber volume fraction is 0.75, which is viewed as the maximum allowable fiber volume fraction feasible to still allow for full fiber wetting throughout the cross-section. If the required strength properties of the structure cannot be met with the maximum allowable fiber volume fraction, the area of the composite must be increased, and the iteration process begins again with the new area of composite.

The second main area of research was on DH-FRP structural shapes. This utilized a combination of hand-layup and braidtrusion to manufacture a 2" by 2" by 48" square shape comprised of a balsa-wood core with carbon fiber braided at varying braid angles around the wood core. The beam was designed with 4 layers of carbon fiber in different orientations. The beam was designed with uni-directional fiber, followed by a braided sleeve at 65° degrees, then an overbraided layer of 45°, and lastly a shallow overbraid of 25°, as seen in Figure 3. Half of the DH-FRP beam cross section is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Cross section of ductile beam.

The failure of the successive layers gives the appearance of yielding. As such, the beam was analyzed as four independent layers. The stress and strain capacity of each layer was calculated as a function of the number of ends of carbon per carrier and the braid angle of that layer. Increasing the braid angle of subsequent layers would increase the strain capacity of the beam. Therefore, the predicted stress-strain behavior of the ductile composite beam was determined as a piece-meal function by connecting the four individual linear stress-strain plots of each layer, to generate a multi-linear stress strain plot for the ductile composite beam, as seen in Figure 4. The failure of each subsequent layer allowed for increased strain capacity, without losing strength capacity in the cross-section. This was achieved by increasing the fiber volume fraction of the fabric layer as the braid angle increased. The values used for the fabric are shown in Table 1. Ultimately, this would give the appearance of a yielding beam and ductile behavior

Table 1: Carbon ends per lamina for a DH-FRP beam.

Lamina Direction	Ends per Carrier
Uni-Directional	2 Top/2 Bottom
75°	3
45°	2
25°	1

Figure 4: Theoretical stress-strain behavior of a ductile composite beam.

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

Two testing programs were conducted: 1) manufacturing and testing of model DH-FRP rebar and 2) manufacturing and testing of carbon DH-FRP beams.

Materials and Properties

The DH-FRP rebar used a material hybridization of Kevlar 49 and carbon fiber. The carbon fiber beam was constructed using a combination of both hand layup and braiding techniques. Two different types of carbon were used, one was specified for the hand layup while the other was used for the braid yarns. The material properties and use of the different carbon fibers used are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Carbon fiber material properties.

Carbon	σ_u (ksi)	E (ksi)	ϵ_u (in/in)	Denier (g/9000m)	ρ (in/lb ³)	Use	Manufacturer
34-700WD	650	34000	0.019	28800	0.065	Hand-Layup	Grafil, Inc.
34-12K WD	700	34000	0.020	7200	0.065	Braid	Grafil, Inc.

The thicker denier carbon was used for the hand layup as the required denier for the uni-directional fiber in order to achieve the desired strength properties. The “WD” designation in the fiber name represents that the fiber is a ‘flat-tow’ fiber, which means that the individual fibers are flat on all sides or rectangular in shape. Flat-tow fibers are ideal for hand-layup applications as the fiber’s natural tendency is to lay flat on a surface.

Manufacturing Process

The beam consisted of a balsa wood core and carbon fiber overlay which would act as the flexural resisting system of the beam. The balsa wood originally had sharp corners from milling it down to the required dimensions. The edges of the balsa wood were rounded off along the entire length of the beam to reduce the localized stress the fibers would encounter at the corners of the beam during the braiding process. The core was then coated in two coats of epoxy in order to prevent the wood from absorbing the epoxy applied to the fibers during the hand-layup and braiding processes allowing for full fiber wetting.

A hand layup technique was used to apply the uni-directional fiber, which was the first lamina to be placed on the beam. Two ends of 34-700WD carbon were placed on the top and bottom flanges of the beamy hand-layup methods, see Figure 5. Epoxy was applied to the balsa wood in a thick coat before the carbon was applied.

Figure 5: Hand-layup of uni-directional carbon.

The braided laminas were applied using a 16 carrier braiding machine. The ends of the yarns were collected and pre-braided for 4” before the beam was fed into the braid. The

beam was fed through the back of the braiding machine and pulled through the front by hand, as seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Braiding of carbon beam viewing (a) back and (b) front of the machine.

The braiding machine was set to a low braid speed to ensure that there was better control of the braid angle and location of the braid point. After the full length of the bar had been braided, the braid was continued for 4" behind the wood to ensure that the braid would not unravel before the epoxy was applied. Epoxy was applied to the fibers after each run through the machine. In total the beam was braided 3 times.

Test Setup and Procedure

The composite beam was tested in 3-point bending in order to achieve a region of constant moment in the middle of the span. Two hydraulic pistons were placed 1 ft (0.3 m) apart from each other centered over the center span of the beam. Underneath each of the loading pistons was placed a 3" x 3" x 1/4" steel plate in order to distribute the load from the piston over the cross-section of the beam and reduce the risk of punching shear in the top flange of the beam. Midspan deflections were measured using an LVDT centered on the beam. The beam was supported on either end by roller supports. The complete test-setup can be seen below in Figure 7 and the test is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7: DH-FRP beam test set-up.

Figure 8: DH-FRP beam testing.

Test Results

Shown in Figure 9 is a representative experimental stress-strain curve of DH-FRP rebar, obtained from a uniaxial tension test on the Kevlar 49/ P-55S material system with the theoretical prediction using the FADM. Shown in Figure 10 is the load-displacement curve for a representative carbon DH-FRP beam.

It is obvious from both results that either tri-linear (Figure 9) or bi-linear (Figure 10) behavior exists, with a definite yield point and a failure point higher than yield. The rebar had tri-linear behavior due to the progressive failure of the carbon core prior to load transfer to the Kevlar sleeve. The carbon beams (Figure 10) failed by local buckling of the compression side of the beam under the point of load application. However, significant yielding did occur prior to failure.

Figure 9: Experimental stress-strain behaviour of DH-FRP rebar.

Figure 10: Experimental load-deflection behaviour of DH-FRP carbon beam.

CONCLUSIONS

The Ductile Hybrid-Fiber Reinforced Polymer (DH-FRP) elements show much promise in the design of structures for civil engineering infrastructure where ductility is needed, especially in areas of moderate to high seismicity. The stress-strain behavior predicted by the FADM and verified experimentally, show a material with high initial stiffness, a definite yield point, an ultimate load greater than the yield load, and high energy absorption capacity illustrated by a large area under the stress-strain curve. With this ability to absorb energy, the DHFRP bar could be used in the design of R/C structures in regions of moderate to high seismicity.

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